

Real-Time Edge Framework (RTEF): Decentralized Decision Making for Offloading

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Abstract—Edge Computing (EC) performs computation at the close proximity to the end devices and reduces dependency to the Cloud and Internet. It also overcomes the Quality of Service (QoS) and latency issues that come naturally from the best-effort behaviour of the Cloud. Although reduced dependency to the Internet enables the application of the EC to the real-time applications, without a standard architecture, EC benefits cannot be incorporated. To this end, in our previous papers, we proposed a novel software reference architecture (SRA) for Edge Servers. The SRA allows receiving Edge Computing benefits without worrying about setup or configuration, but only focusing on software development. Regardless of the computing power of the Edge Servers, the architecture enables a decentralised (real-time) task execution at the edge. Once a task request arrives, the receiving server determines whether to execute the task on itself or offload it to any of the neighbouring servers, by considering several parameters, such as latency, and available resources. In this paper, we explain how servers decide where to execute the task, without requiring a centralized load balancer. Moreover, we show how they share their resources between each other to create a common knowledge of their neighbouring servers.

Index Terms—real-time computing, edge computing, task offloading, fog computing, decentralized load balancer.

I. INTRODUCTION

Computing has always switched between centralised and decentralized computing since the 1960s. In the 1960s, local terminals did not have enough computing power, and thus the computations were performed on hosts (servers). The optimizations were also focused on the limited resources of the hosts [1]. Until the 1980s, the computation was centralized. Centralized systems tend to have lower administrative and operational costs, and their configurations are more straightforward compared to the decentralized systems [2]. Until the 2000s, the widespread use of personal computers and increased resources such as computing power on these systems, enabled computation directly on the client machines, eliminating the need of a centralized server [1]. From the 2000s, computing started its journey back to its origins: decentralization [2]. A decentralized system is a system in which each participant is controlled by itself, and the results are aggregated to create a universal system response [3]. It can be other mechanisms that monitor decentralized participants, but the hierarchical structure is minimized. In case of a failure, automatic recovery is only possible with a decentralized system. Decentralized systems also increase flexibility, autonomy, and responsiveness [4], [5]. However, the development, maintenance, and management of these systems are involved. This complexity pushed the computing and storage back to the server-side [1]. The procedure of computation and storage in remote servers is called Cloud Computing. Sharing the unused computing power to balance the workload was one of the most significant advantages of Cloud Computing, or "the Cloud." Moreover, the Cloud reduced the marginal cost of the system administration and expenditure to create a data centre.

Cloud Computing mostly depends on the Internet and provides best-effort servicing. Therefore, it cannot be utilized in the areas where the timing is critical or with no Internet access. To perform (near) real-time operations, the computation needs to be close to the field or device tier to minimize the network disruptions. Edge Computing (EC) brings computational power near the user as close as possible [6]. Hence, it is expected to solve the two issues that are mentioned above: Low-latency and high Quality of Service (QoS). Moreover, having the data close to the source reduces security risks by giving more control over the sensitive data.

In our previous paper on EC [6], we proposed a conceptual software reference architecture (SRA) for Edge Servers, to realise a real-time capable server framework, together with its requirements and enablers. This SRA is designed in such a way that it does not limit the language nor hardware to create an instance from it. The SRA enabled seamless execution of the real-time tasks in a resource-aware Edge Network. Each server using the framework based on the SRA is considered as an Edge Server. The Edge Network is created automatically as connections between these servers are established. There is no limitation on the topology, and any of the available topologies can be used for connection (See Fig. 1). Then, the servers start a handshaking phase to introduce themselves to each other. The servers exchange their resources as well as available services, which are wrappers for the programs/software/command (PSC). The architecture allows message exchanging between each Edge Server in the network, even if they do not have a direct connection between each other. Once an Edge Server receives a task request for the

execution of a PSC, the deadline and estimated runtime of the task, available resources of all Edge Servers in the network, and the shortest distances between them are collected. This information is used to determine an optimal server to execute this task without missing its deadline. Depending on the availability and optimality, an Edge Server can either execute the task on itself or offload the task to another Edge Server. If it is going to be executed on the receiving server, considering the possible other running tasks, the incoming task must be scheduled based on its type and parameters. Otherwise, the Edge Server must choose an optimal Edge Server to offload the task to. The task scheduling methods to plan the execution is explained in our other work [7]. This paper will explain how an Edge Server makes decisions, either to offload or execute a task on itself.

Fig. 1. Any number of Edge Servers can be connected with each other using any of the available topologies to create an Edge Network. The architecture allows them to communicate with each other, whether they are directly connected with each other or not.

II. ONLINE DECISION MAKING IN DECENTRALIZED ENVIRONMENTS

A task is a program, software, or command (PSC). According to their arrival patterns, tasks, in general, can be classified into three categories [8]. These types define whether a scheduling algorithm can be applied to them or not. *Periodic* tasks are the tasks that arrive at a constant rate. The time between activations is called a period. They have an infinite sequence of identical activities. *Aperiodic* tasks are usually event-driven. They can run once or infinite times, but their inter-arrival time is not bound to any value. During design time, their arrival times are not known a priori. *Sporadic* tasks are aperiodic tasks, but the inter-arrival times are bounded by a minimal inter-arrival time.

In our proposed architecture [6], a task (a PSC) cannot be directly executed, but only be requested for execution. Tasks are wrapped with services that define their behaviours and how they should be executed. A service has several parameters to be set, based on the software behaviour such as execution duration, relative deadline, CPU affinities, and execution utilization (maximum CPU utilization/bandwidth).

TABLE I
A LIST OF EXAMPLE PSCS WITH DIFFERENT SERVICE TYPES.

PSC	Service Type	WCET	Period	Relative Deadline
A	Legacy	3	N/A	6
B	Simple	3	N/A	6
C	Simple Periodic	3	6	6

Based on the three task types, we introduced three service types that wrap tasks depending on their behaviours [7]:

1) *Legacy*: Legacy services are created for non-resumable PSCs, which cannot be resumed when paused. They can either run until completion, or terminated. Their execution restarts from beginning after being terminated. Once the execution is completed, its task is removed.

2) *Simple*: Simple services are created for PSCs that get continuous or streaming data, or that can be paused. Similar to Legacy services, they also wrap *aperiodic* tasks. They can be paused at anytime, and resumed from where they left off. For example, a video application can be wrapped with a Simple service.

3) *Simple Periodic*: Simple Periodic services are repeating Simple services, which wrap *periodic* tasks. They are expected to arrive at constant rates. Collecting data from sensors, or control loops can be given as examples. The scheduling algorithm should plan their arrival in the future and allocate necessary resources beforehand to keep them running without deadline misses.

Table I lists three PSC examples, each defined with a different type of service. As expected, while *A* and *B* have no period for being aperiodic PSCs, *C* has a period of 6 time units. All of the PSCs have the worst-case execution time (WCET) of 3 time units. If they are preempted at time $t=2$ and resumed at $t=3$, they are expected to run as illustrated in Fig. 2. As seen

from the figure, when preempted, the previous runtime of A in Legacy service type is lost, causing it to run another three time units until its completion at $t = 6$. B in Simple type remembered the runtime, causing it to run only one more time unit until completion at $t = 4$. Similarly, C in Simple Periodic completed execution at $t = 4$ and its second period started at $t = 6$, idling the CPU for two units of time. If they would be resumed at $t = 4$, there would have been not enough time to complete execution of A on time, hence causing a deadline miss. Depending on the criticality of a task, deadline misses can be fatal.

In addition to the execution times, in a decentralized system, if a task is offloaded to another server, the delay to offload is also added to the execution time. The delay is accumulated until the task request reaches its final destination. If the task sends no response, it is one-directional and its delay multiplier is 1. If it sends a response, then it is bi-directional and its delay is multiplied by 2.

A. Assumptions

In order to realize the concepts explained throughout the paper, the following assumptions have been made.

Fig. 2. An example of the execution behaviours of independent PSCs in Legacy, Simple and Simple Periodic service types on different computers when they are preempted at $t = 2$ and resumed at $t = 3$.

According to Garey and Johnson [9], general scheduling problems are NP-hard. In practice, it means that, if the number of tasks rises, the time for finding a feasible schedule grows exponentially. In this paper, it is assumed that the computations for finding an optimal server to offload have no or negligible overheads, regardless of the task count.

For real-time applications, the scheduling is more critical, especially for hard real-time tasks. Real-time systems are usually built using dedicated custom hardware. However, custom hardware is expensive and prone to errors. They are usually designed for custom tasks, and they have reduced reusability. Besides, upgrades are also hard to perform and expensive. Another way of building a real-time system is by using a mix of hardware and a Real-Time Operating System (RTOS). The utilization of the hardware and RTOS reduces the development and maintenance times, therefore the costs. The approach also reduces the burden on upgrades. Custom hardware for dedicated tasks is formally verified to ensure the functionality in all situations. However, it is quite hard to verify sophisticated hardware designed for multi-purposes, formally. Therefore, it is assumed that hardware used for the concepts are real-time proven.

The schedulers require several properties of the processes known in advance. One of them is the WCET. Determining this value is quite intricate and requires in-depth analysis. Structural analysis is one of the analyses that can be performed on the source code, object code, or the assembly code. Each of these has both advantages and disadvantages. Source code analysis requires access to the source code of the process. It is the purest form and more comfortable to understand compared to the other two structures. However, the analysis may not give concrete results, as the program depends on the preprocessors, linkers, macros, and the compiler. Object code analysis is done on the code after compiling optimizations are done. However, it is harder to analyse as much information is lost. Assembly code has the same issues listed for object code. This makes the analysis even harder due to assembly being lower-level. The WCET analysis also requires a deep understanding of the hardware that the software is laid on. In this paper, it is assumed that the WCET values of the PSCs are known a priori.

The research also assumes that the PSCs do not suspend themselves before their execution is completed. Moreover, running PSCs are thought to be independent of each other, and they have protection for critical section usage.

If a system comprises more than one computer, on top of the complexity of the scheduling problems, additionally, intercommunication comes into the play. There are several load balancers (e.g. Seesaw, HAProxy, LoadMaster) and schedulers (e.g. Slurm) that manage a fair distribution of the tasks with balanced hardware resources. However, either they are centralized or not developed for real-time computing. This paper will introduce a decision-making algorithm for decentralized load balancing. The intercommunication is out of the scope of the paper, it is assumed that the network message exchange is real-time, e.g. using real-time communication technologies such as Time-Sensitive Networking (TSN), and the network delays are known.

Finally, to reduce the complexity of the problem, it is assumed that hardware has unlimited memory and disk space.

B. Decision Making for Offloading

The final location to execute tasks is determined by the Edge Server that initially receives the request. It might be the case that the receiving server does not have enough resources to execute the task on time. In this case, the task is forwarded to another server in the Edge Network. Forwarding a task request to another server is called *offloading*. Offloading arises due to limited resource availability, power limitation, mobility of the End Device, or network limitation [10]. Decision mechanisms play a vital role during offloading for optimal performance. If the network consists of multiple Edge Servers, it is then possible to offload the task request to another Edge Server. Offloading follows the flow seen in Fig. 3.

Once the task is received, first, the server lists all available Edge Servers that have the service defined for that task. If the receiving server has enough resources to run the task, it plans the execution [7]. If not, an Edge Server in the Edge Network is searched, which can complete the execution in the shortest time. To find an adequate server E in the network N , when a user (or an End Device) A requests the task T_i , the satisfaction equation seen in Eq. 1 and Eq. 2 can be used. The equation calculates the maximum duration to execute a task on a server, including the delay and currently used CPU. Below, this satisfaction equation S is explained. Assume

$$\forall E \in N \Rightarrow S_j(E_j, T_i) \quad (1)$$

where

$$S_j(E_j, T_i) = \max \left(\left\{ \left(\frac{x_i u_i}{p_j F_{k,j}} + w_i D_{A,j} \right) f_{i,k} : k = 1 \dots c \right\} \right) \quad (2)$$

and where $F_{k,j}$ is the free available CPU percentage of core k in server j , $D_{A,j}$ is the minimum delay between the task requester A and Edge Server E_j . $f_{i,k}$ is 1 if T_i has an affinity to core k , 0 if not. w_i is the delay multiplier, and 1 if T_i is one-directional, 2 if bi-directional. x_i is the WCET of the task in terms of MI, p_j is the total speed of the server j in terms of MIPS, and u_i is the CPU utilization in percentage allowed for task i , where $0\% < u_i \leq 100\%$.

Fig. 3. The flowchart of the decision mechanisms for selection of an optimal server to offload the task. Plan execution has its flowchart depicted in Fig. ??

Assume that S' is a subset of all S that satisfies $S_j \leq d_i + a_i$ where d_i is the relative deadline of T_i in terms of MIPS and a_i is the arrival time of the task request at the first Edge Server E . Then, the index of $\min(S')$ defines which server should be chosen for execution.

If there are more than one indices that provide the same $\min(S')$ value, Edge Server E_j giving $\min(D_{A,j})$ receives the task. The decision using the equation gives a correct result at the time that the request is made. However, in real life, this calculation takes some time, which may use outdated information due to, e.g., a new execution of a task on another server. There are several research activities on offloading [11], [12], each focusing on possible policies such as power consumption,

response time, availability of the server, or computing capability. These mostly focus on reducing the delay using probabilities and average values of the computation timing, which is not applicable in a real-time scenario.

The architecture suggests and follows the following steps in order to choose the most convenient server for task execution. If a step cannot determine a single server, the next step evaluates the situation. The steps are also shown as a flowchart in Fig. 3.

- 1) Each Edge Server has an updated list of the available resources and services together with their locations [6]. First, the current server queries the possible locations for the requested task, including itself.
- 2) If the current server does not contain the service for this task or does not have enough resources, then, an alternative server in the Edge Network is looked up.
- 3) In case multiple alternatives can execute the task on time, the server which can execute the task in the shortest time is chosen.
- 4) If the resources are the same, then, the server with the smallest delay is chosen.
- 5) If latencies are also the same, then, one of the servers is chosen randomly.
- 6) If no server found that can execute the task, then the current server tries to plan the execution, following "no" in multiple alternatives branches. In this case, the chosen server will be itself.

Once the task request is offloaded, the chosen server devises an execution plan. The execution plan checks whether the task can directly be executed, or any preparations for the task should be made. If the sum of execution utilizations (CPU utilization) of all running tasks, including the requested task, does not exceed 100% at each CPU, then the tasks can run without further action. Otherwise, one possibility is to scale down the CPU utilization of the newly requested task, already running tasks or all tasks [7].

Scheduling the tasks is a fallback situation, in the case that downscaling does not yield a feasible solution. To schedule tasks in Simple Periodic type, the architecture uses the Earliest Deadline First (EDF) scheduling. For tasks in Legacy and Simple type, Non-resumable And Preemptible Aperiodic TASK (NAPATA) scheduling is used. The novel NAPATA scheduling algorithm is explained in our another paper [7]. If the scheduling is also not possible, the task fails to execute. At the moment, no precautions are taken if such a situation occurs. However, possible fail-safe actions can be considered. For example, as future work, termination of lower priority tasks is planned.

Fig. 4. Experiment setup and plan for an Edge Network using four End Devices and two Edge Services

III. VALIDATION

The algorithms and equations are integrated into the Real-Time Edge Framework (RTEF), which is based on the architecture proposed in [6]. Then the framework is tested on a virtual environment in simulation mode. The environment contains three Edge Servers (ES) and four End Devices (ED). Edge Servers are used to execute the tasks, and End Devices are used to request the tasks. ES 1 has two identical CPUs, and other servers have only single CPUs. Each CPU has 1 MIPS execution speed (p). ES 1 is connected to ES 2, and the delay between them is one time unit. ES 1 also has connections to ED 1, ED 2, and ED 3. ES 2 is connected to ED 4 and ES 3. Latencies between End Devices and the Edge Servers are neglected. Services A, B, C, D, E, F are defined with the parameters listed in Table II. All tasks, hence their services are one-directional. Service A is created in all servers, using the same behaviour. Services B, C, D , and E are created only on ES 1, and Service F only on ES 2 and ES 3. ED 1, 2, and 3 request tasks from ES 1 at $t = 0$ to execute A, B , and E , respectively. At the same time, ED 4 requests F from ES 2. At $t = 2$, ED 1 also requests an instance of C and ED 2 requests D . The experiment setup and plan are summarised in Fig. 4.

If the earliest deadline takes the higher priority, at $t = 0$, the execution order of the tasks on ES 1 becomes B, E , and A . E uses CPU 2; however, A and B share the same CPU, CPU 1. They both require 100% CPU utilization. According to the priorities, B must be executed first. However, executing A after B (at $t = 3$) would cause A to miss its absolute deadline, which is its arrival time plus relative deadline ($a_A + d_A = 8$). To prevent this situation, first, the possibility of downscaling is

evaluated. WCET of B is equal to its relative deadline. Therefore, downscaling the CPU usage of B is not possible. Then, another alternative server within the network is searched. ES 2 and 3 also have service A, and the request can be offloaded to those servers. The transfer of the request takes one (ES 2) or two time units (ES 3) due to the delay between the servers. If ES 3 was not in the network, at $t = 1$ on ES 2, the possibility of on-time execution of tasks F and A would need to be evaluated. This would require downscaling and scheduling tests on ES 2. As mentioned earlier, the decision mechanism evaluates the resource availabilities of the servers that contain the service, and chooses the fastest server first. ES 1 is busy with running A, it has no available CPU at the moment. However, the calculation also includes this server as well. Evaluating the availabilities of all servers using Eq. 2 gives:

$$S_1(E_1, T_1) = \max \left(\left\{ \left(\frac{x_1 100}{(1)F_{k,1}} + (1)(0) \right) f_{1,k} : k = 1, 2 \right\} \right) \quad (3)$$

$$= \max \left(\left\{ \left(\frac{(6)(100)}{(1)(0)} + (1)(0) \right) 1, \left(\frac{(6)(100)}{(1)(0)} + (1)(0) \right) 0 \right\} \right) \quad (4)$$

$$= \text{Not Feasible} \quad (5)$$

$$S_2(E_2, T_1) = \max \left(\left\{ \left(\frac{x_1 100}{(1)F_{k,1}} + (1)(1) \right) f_{1,k} : k = 1 \right\} \right) \quad (6)$$

$$= \max \left(\left\{ \left(\frac{(6)(100)}{(1)(0)} + (1)(1) \right) 1 \right\} \right) \quad (7)$$

$$= \text{Not Feasible} \quad (8)$$

$$S_3(E_3, T_1) = \max \left(\left\{ \left(\frac{x_1 100}{(1)F_{k,3}} + (1)(2) \right) f_{1,k} : k = 1 \right\} \right) \quad (9)$$

$$= \max \left(\left\{ \left(\frac{(6)(100)}{(1)(100)} + (1)(2) \right) 1 \right\} \right) \quad (10)$$

$$= 8 \leq 8 + 0 \quad (11)$$

$\min(S_1, S_2, S_3)$ results in S_3 , choosing the server to offload to be ES 3.

C and D task requests arrive at $t=2$. Both have one thread at each CPU due to their allowed CPU property and thread per core parameters. At this time unit, ES 1 and its CPU is entirely available. Both tasks can be scheduled according to EDF scheduling. However, the server downscales first, as scheduling is considered as a fallback solution. Downscaling CPU execution capacities of both tasks to 50% doubles execution times of both tasks, but they can still complete their executions before missing their deadlines. The resulting scheduling diagram is shown in Fig. 5.

The service creator is expected to create a feasible distribution of tasks in Edge Servers during design time. In case a feasible scheduling not to be found, that task will not be executed.

IV. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

Edge Computing (EC) paradigm can be used to solve latency and Quality of Service (QoS) problems that the Cloud Computing has. It is one of the recent technologies that can be applied in real-time computing due to being close to the data source. A reference architecture must be proposed, and its standards must be defined to get its benefits entirely. Our architecture proposed in [6] started from the definition, listed the requirements and proposed a software reference architecture (SRA) to exploit EC benefits and build a decentralized Edge Network.

One feature of Edge Computing is to offload the tasks to other neighbouring Edge Servers in case a task cannot be executed until its deadline. This paper introduced a satisfaction equation that can be used for decentralized offloading decisions in Edge Networks. The equation needs CPU availabilities of all Edge Servers in the network and the characteristics of the tasks. Based on the calculation results, the initial recipient of the task chooses an Edge Server that can execute the task. The calculations are assumed to have negligible overheads.

The paper concluded with a validation scenario. The scenario tested the behaviour of the system as the tasks are requested at different times. It covered offloading a task to another Edge Server in the same network in case of unavailable CPU resources. In the simulation environment, the results were seen as expected and the concept is validated.

Currently, if there are no alternative servers in the network that can schedule the incoming task, the task fails to execute. However, as future work, either the lower priority tasks can be terminated, preempted or downscaled with the cost of missing its deadline. Moreover, as its current state, the feasibility of running tasks must be manually verified by the user. In the future, possible deadline misses can be checked by simulating the task requests with different combinations. Lastly, task migration can be implemented, to offload a running task to continue execution on another Edge Server.

TABLE II
AN EXAMPLE SET OF PRE-DEFINED SERVICES WITH DEFINED EXECUTION BEHAVIOURS OF TASKS. ALL TASKS ARE ONE-DIRECTIONAL.

Service	WCET	Relative Deadline	Type	Allowed CPUs	Max. CPU Utilization %	Thread per Core	Available on
A	6	8	Legacy	1	100	1	1,2
B	3	3	Legacy	1	100	1	1
C	4	8	S.Periodic	1,2	100	1	1
D	3	6	S.Periodic	1,2	100	1	1
E	2	5	Simple	2	100	1	1
F	2	9	Simple	1	100	1	2

Fig. 5. Resulting scheduling diagram based on the experiment defined in Fig. 4 and Table II.

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